

Investigating mass loss from RSG and AGB stars using the new VLT-MATISSE imaging instrument

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Cycle of matter

Open questions

- How is the atmosphere elevated, in particular for red supergiants. Are there physical processes missing in current models?
- Which is the dust condensation sequence, and how does it depend on the type of star and the stellar parameters?
- How does the mass loss rate relate to the stellar parameters?
- Which is the composition of the dust that is returned to the interstellar medium?
- Which is the effect of close companions?

Sketch of a Mira star

The photospheres and innermost CSEs of only the very few apparently largest stars can be resolved by AO-assisted instruments.

A larger sample requires optical interferometry.

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|-----------------------------------|-----------------------------------|
| Stellar photosphere | : PIONIER, GRAVITY (SPHERE, ALMA) |
| Extended molecular atmosphere: | GRAVITY, MATISSE (SPHERE, ALMA) |
| Dust formation | : MATISSE |
| Larger CSE. | : ALMA (CO, other molecules) |
| Maser (SiO, H ₂ O, OH) | : VLBA, MERLIN, ALMA |

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The VLTI and its instruments

■ VLTI

- Four 8.2-m Unit Telescopes (UTs)
- Four relocatable 1.8-m Auxiliary Telescopes (ATs)
 - Small configuration:
 - Medium configuration:
 - Large configuration:
- Dedicated imaging scheme
- All current instruments combine 4 beams
- Spatial resolution at longest AT baseline (130m currently) between ~ 1.2 mas at 1.5 μm to ~10 mas at 13 μm

- CfP for P108 is out with deadline 25 March

■ PIONIER, near-IR H band

- 1.5-1.8 μm
- Spectral resolution ~35 or undispersed

■ GRAVITY, near-IR K band

- 2.0-2.4 μm
- Spectral resolutions 22, 500, 4000
- Astrometric mode

■ MATISSE, thermal-IR LMN bands

- L/M bands (3.2-3.9 μm / 4.5-5.0 μm) with spectral resolutions 30, 500, 1000, 3500
- N band (8-13 μm) with spectral resolutions 30, 220

VY CMa: Extended atmosphere

Wittkowski et al. 2012

■ Bumpy visibility curve

➤ Resembles Mira stars

Mira star S Ori,
Same AMBER mode
Wittkowski et al. 2008

➤ Indicative of extended atmospheric molecular layers (CO, H₂O)

➤ Broad-band observations over-estimate the photospheric diameter

➤ Revised (smaller) photospheric radius: 1420 +/- 120 R_{sun}

■ Strong closure phase signal

➤ Indicative of deviations from point symmetry in molecular layers

■ Over-resolved background (dust)

Mira stars: Comparison to 1D and 3D dynamic models

- Confirmation of spatially extended molecular atmospheres above the continuum radii
- Both modeling attempts provided satisfactory fits to our data.
- Shocks induced by convection and pulsation in the 3D CO5BOLD models of AGB stars are roughly spherically expanding and of similar nature to those of self-excited pulsations in 1D CODEX models.

Comparison to

- CODEX 1D dynamic model atmospheres (blue)
- Azimuthally averaged intensities based on CO5BOLD 3D dynamic model atmospheres (red)

Model intensity profiles

2.0 μ m: water vapour

2.25 μ m: near-continuum

2.29 μ m: CO (2-1) bandhead

2.47 μ m: CO

RSGs and comparison to dynamic model atmospheres

- The observed extensions of atmospheric layers of a sample of RSGs are comparable to those of Mira stars.
- This not predicted by any of the considered model atmospheres including available 3D convection and new 1D pulsation models of RSGs.
- Convection or pulsation alone cannot levitate the molecular atmospheres of RSGs.

Levitation of RSG atmospheres: ideas

- Radiatively driven extension caused by radiation pressure on Doppler-shifted molecular lines (Josselin & Plez & 2007)

- Acceleration on dust grains that may form already close to the stellar photosphere (Verhoelst et al. 2006, 2009; Speck et al. 2000; Scicluna et al. 2015, Gail et al. 2020): Al₂O₃, metallic iron, or other large transparent grains such as Ca-Al-rich silicates possibly as close as $\sim 2 R_{\text{star}}$
- Alfvén wave – driven winds (Auriere et al. 2010, Cranmer & Saar 2011, Thirumalai & Heyl 2012)

The dimming of Betelgeuse – process for RSGs in general?

- Discrete highly localised mass ejection event, possibly connected to photospheric motion caused by a stochastic occurrence of an extreme convection cell. Possibly enhanced by pulsation (Dupree et al. 2020; Harper et al. 2020, Montarges submitted).
- Discrete mass ejections may also explain the mass-loss history of the red hypergiant VY CMa, and of RSGs in general (Humphreys et al. 2020).

The surface structure of the red supergiant V602 Car

- VLT-PIONIER H-band ($1.5\text{-}1.8\ \mu\text{m}$) imaging at two epochs, 2016 and 2019
- Image reconstruction with SQUEEZE (Baron et al. 2010) and IRBIS (Hofmann et al. 2014)
- Visibilities indicate an extended molecular layer

V602 Car: comparison to 3D RHD simulations

Morphology

Contrast

- Reconstructed images are consistent with 3D RHD simulations in terms of morphology and contrast
- Extended molecular layer is not reproduced
- Surface structure related to instationary convection, and convolved to observed spatial resolution

The red supergiant AH Scorpii

- Part of our sample for VLT/AMBER observations (Arroyo-Torres et al. 2013)
- Period 714d (GCVS),
- Distance 2.3+/-0.2 kpc (Chen&Shen 2008)
- Strong narrow 9.7 μm silicate feature (Sloan & Price 1998, Lorenz-Martins & Pompeia 2000, Speck et al. 2000).
- Angular diameter 5.8+/-0.2 mas, 20% of the K-band flux in an over-resolved (dust) component
- Photospheric radius 1411+/- 124 R_{sun}
- Strong atmospheric extension
- $\log L/L_{\text{sun}} = 5.5 \pm 0.3$, initial mass 25-40 M_{sun}
- VLT/PIONIER image shows surface structure (Climent/Wittkowski unpublished)
- Known source of SiO, H₂O, OH masers

L-band medium spectral resolution, center 3.95 μm

N-band low spectral resolution

Preliminary image reconstruction MATISSE L-band across SiO (2-0)

The red supergiant AH Scorpii

Preliminary image reconstruction MATISSE L-band across SiO (2-0)

The red supergiant AH Scorpii

Pseudo-continuum

SiO (2-0) bandhead

Preliminary image reconstruction

MATISSE N-band

The red supergiant AH Scorpii

L-band medium spectral resolution, center $3.95\mu\text{m}$

N-band low spectral resolution

Summary

- Details of the mass-loss process of cool evolved stars are not yet understood
- Current models based on convection and pulsation can reproduce observed extensions for AGB stars, but not for RSG stars by far. This points to a missing physical process in the models.
- PIONIER has proven to be an excellent tool to image stellar surfaces
- The MATISSE instrument at L/M and N bands links to the molecular layers and to the dust formation zone by *imaging* observations
- The L/M and N bands include important lines, such as of SiO gas and silicate dust, helping us to study the depletion of Si into silicate dust
- We observe a significant fraction of the flux in a much extended over-resolved (dust) component in L and N
- RSG and AGB stars are observationally similar in many aspects